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Annotation: The sanctity of the family and the role of a woman in it. A woman is a unique blessing and the main role in the upbringing of children.

Key words: Child upbringing of a woman in the family. Ibo, modesty, modesty.

The family is the main link of human development, the most important institution of the state system, the core and basis of our society. The role and influence of the family in forming and improving the unique spirituality of any nation is incomparable.

Happy families make a happy community. Because happy parents raise happy children, and children of loving parents love each other.

The family is a sacred place that preserves the continuity of every people, the nation, ensures the development of national values, gives birth to a new generation, educates it spiritually and physically, and is considered the main foundation of society. Family is one of the most beautiful miracles of nature, it is a social unit based on "natural-biological", economic, legal, spiritual relations typical of humans.

Family is the most important part of people's life, the base of civil society. In this holy place, a person is born, it is here that he matures spiritually and morally.

The following conditions are expected for the emergence and rule of love in the family:

- mutual respect of family members;
- trust and protection of family members;
- closeness, mutual support and sharing of ideas;
- sense of responsibility (parents' sense of their duties and responsibilities);
- to fight against difficulties together and solve them;
- to be able to express one's identity and create a suitable environment for living happily;
- have a healthy material and spiritual life;

The needs listed above should be met in the family environment.

Family is sacred, woman is sacred in it. She is the symbol of female beauty, the lamp of the holy fortress called the family, the holy breed that embodies all virtues. A woman is a mother, a woman is a unique blessing.

The one who makes a family a family is a woman. The one who unites the family and our society, brings blessings to it, illuminates our homes with the light of love, elegance, and goodness, are actually our honorable mothers, our virtuous sisters.

Chastity is a characteristic and appropriate for women. His face always shines. Andisha is happy with the light of modesty and intelligence.

It is known that the role and influence of the family, and the woman in the family, is incomparable in the formation and promotion of the unique spirituality of the nation. The role of mothers is incomparable in the birth of a healthy child and its intellectual and spiritual growth. The purest and purest feelings of a person, the first life concepts and imaginations are formed first of all in the bosom of the family and with mother's education. For this, the mother herself must be spiritually healthy and enlightened. The position of the women of our country in the society, their

relationship with the family, their role in the social life is extremely important, so their position is highly valued in all aspects.

If the family is strong and healthy, the child will be mature. The child provides the life expectancy of the adult. Among the beautiful human qualities in the family, first of all, he is a perfect person, shrewd, thoughtful, intelligent, the right word, polite, consistent, respect for elders, honor for children, humanity, kindness, loyalty to one's country. virtues are formed in the family. A mother's love for her child is one of the human qualities. Mother's sacred duty is first of all to raise a healthy child.

Not to raise the voice of human beauties to children, that is, to speak in a low voice. Beauty is first of all in keeping a household, maintaining order depends on the taste and wisdom of a woman, teaching order and teaching them to children.

Human beauty is a sign of culture to dress with taste. Home clothes are different, street clothes are different. To teach that the clothes you wear for holidays are different depending on your age.

When cooking with love, pay attention to cleanliness first. Designing a vegetable slicer. Teaching to pay attention to the plates.

To prepare the child for independent life, we should pay attention to the following.

1. Oriental rules of etiquette in the family;
2. In the spirit of respect and example for national values;
3. The place and dignity of the elderly in the family;
4. To strengthen the virtue of honesty and integrity in a boy;
5. Modesty, diligence, honesty in a girl;
6. Father's place in the family.

"The future of the nation is in the hands of mothers," wrote one of the great ones. In this short and concise phrase, the role of a woman on the world stage, her honorable duty and great responsibility are literally expressed. Historical sources testify that the strength of the nation, the freedom of the homeland and the happiness of people are determined by the perfection of these noble breeds.

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It is known that the role and influence of the family, and the woman in the family, is incomparable in forming and raising the unique spirituality of the nation. Mothers are primarily responsible for the birth of a healthy child and for its intellectual and spiritual growth. First of all, the mother is the one who cares the most for the child to be healthy and mature, educated and talented, spiritual and enlightened. Mothers' wit and wisdom are very important in the education of girls, morals, broad thinking as a future mother, the formation of concepts of duty and responsibility in boys, courage and pride, honor and honor.

Today, the fact that the women of our country recognize their honorable duty as sacred and perform it honestly and impartially is appreciated in every way.

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